

Analysis of the Current Traceability Process and Needs for improvement.

Case study

Purpose of the Interview:

1. To find out their traceability needs
2. To find out how they currently handle traceability management
 - a. What is the current process?
 - b. What are the tools being used?
3. To find out what traceability gaps they have (needs) and possible solutions that could work for them

Research questions?

1. What are the traceability needs for a mortgage brokering company?
2. What are the challenges of establishing traceability in this domain?
3. What are the uses of traceability in this domain?
 - a. How do they differ with uses in other domains? – retrospective.

Before the interview

1. Introduce myself
2. Ask if I can record the interview

Background of the interviewee

1. What is your role in the company? (*What do you do?*)
2. For how long have you worked in this role?
3. What are other roles that you have had in the past at the company?
4. What development process do you follow? (*e.g., V model, Agile, in-between?*)

Preparation/Planning

Purpose of traceability

1. What is traceability for you?
2. Why do you need traceability links?
 - a. Apart from the current use case, do you have other areas in your development where you need traceability?

Artifacts

1. Which artifacts do you have in your development environment?
 - a. Requirements/Features
 - b. Models

- c. Wikis
- d. Code
- e. Tests
- f. Tickets

*Ask about tools for each artifact if not mentioned with the artifacts.

2. How are these artifacts related to each other? Derived, generated, refined (etc)
3. Do you create traceability links between these files? If yes, how is this done? (e.g, through copying IDs from one file to another?)
4. What is the problem with the way the current links are created?
5. In your opinion, what would be a perfect way to create links? Imagine no tool restriction.
6. What do you think about automatic generation of trace links?

Link Types

1. Are you aware of the term "link type"?
 - a. If yes, what link types do you know of?
 - b. If no, explain what link types are and give examples.
2. In your company, is there a need to have more than one link type or is it enough to have one generic link?
 - a. If yes, why? And which types?
3. What kind of information should traceability links contain?
 - a. Does it make sense to add meta data like, created-by, modified-by/on, reason for existence of T-link and so on?
4. For your role, are high level traceability links better than low level (detailed) traceability links? Why?

Creation/Maintenance

1. When should which traceability links be created? In a particular step in the development?
2. When should traceability links be updated?
 - a. What should trigger the update?
 - b. How do you identify which links need to change?
 - c. Who should update the links?

Communication/Collaboration

1. Do you think traceability information should be shared between teams? If yes, why?
2. How should this information be shared?
 - a. Process-wise
 - b. Tool-wise

Output

1. How do you currently store traceability links?/ How do you want the links to be stored?
2. Do you version traceability links?
3. Are there any challenges with respect to the storage and versioning of traceability links?

4. Are there tools that you know of that solve these challenges?

Uses

1. What do you use the traceability links for?
2. Are there links that are only created and not used?
3. Do you have any tools for visualization of your traceability links?
 - a. If yes, on a scale from 1 – 10, how satisfied are you with this visualization?
 - b. What would it take for a visualization tool to be at 10 on the scale? Which visualization features are important to you?
4. Do you perform or would like to perform any kind of analysis on the traceability links?
 - a. If yes, which kind of analysis? E.g., How the software looks like, dependency between artifacts etc.
 - b. Do you have tools that can perform analysis on your traceability links? If yes, do the tools support custom queries on the traceability links?
 - c. On a scale from 1 – 10, how satisfied are you with these analysis tools?
 - d. What are the missing features that will put the analysis tools at 10 on the scale?

Measurements

1. What do you think about the effort of establishing traceability links? Is it something worthwhile?
2. Can you think of how to measure the quality of traceability links? E.g. completeness, correctness
 - a. Do you currently use any of these?
3. How do you know that you have enough, too little or too much traceability links?
4. Are there any standard you follow that mandate you to have traceability links?

Conclusion

1. Summarize what we have learnt in the interview and ask if the interviewee agrees.
2. Do you feel like you have something to add that we missed in the discussion?
3. Can we contact you with follow-up questions for clarification?
4. Thank the interviewee for participating